

Abstract

Traditional Chinese Exercises for Pain Management in Patients with Knee Osteoarthritis – A Review of Meta-analyses.

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Abstract

Background: Knee osteoarthritis (KOA) is a chronic, incurable condition that is a leading cause of pain and functional limitations, significantly diminishing patients' quality of life. Effective management requires a personalised, multimodal approach, with exercise being a key recommended intervention.

Objective: This preliminary review aims to evaluate the existing literature on the effectiveness of Traditional Chinese Exercises (TCE) in managing pain among patients with KOA.

Methods: A comprehensive search of the PubMed database was conducted to identify relevant studies. The review focused on meta-analyses assessing the impact of TCE on pain in KOA patients.

Results: Out of 51 meta-analyses identified, 9 met the inclusion criteria, encompassing 152 randomised controlled trials (RCTs) with a combined total of 10,377 participants. The interventions included Tai Chi (100 RCTs), Baduanjin (31 RCTs), Wuqinxi (11 RCTs), Yijinjing (10 RCTs), and Qi Gong (1 RCT, broadly defined). Pain outcomes were measured using validated tools such as the Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index (WOMAC) and the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). All nine meta-analyses reported significant improvements in pain scores associated with TCE.

Conclusion: Traditional Chinese Exercises appear to be effective in reducing pain among individuals with KOA and should be considered a viable therapeutic option. In addition to pain relief, TCE may also alleviate fatigue, improve mobility, enhance joint range of motion, and contribute to overall improvements in health and quality of life.

Keywords: Traditional Chinese exercises; Pain; Knee; Osteoarthritis.

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